

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

Call: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02

Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

T1.3_Italian Lab 1st Co-creation Workshop Report

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Document history

Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
20/06/2023	1.0	1 st draft by APRE
26/06/2023	2.0	Final version by APRE

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Port Authority of Bari, Piazzale Cristoforo Colombo, 1, 70122 Bari BA, Italy

EVENT DATE: 13 June 2023 (10 – 13 a.m. CEST, 3’)

EVENT TITLE: MARINEWIND: Co-creation Path to Awareness on Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs) / Percorso di co-creazione per uno sviluppo consapevole dell’eolico offshore galleggiante (FOWT)

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: Official Partner of the EMD – European Maritime Day 2023

LEAD ORGANISER: APRE

CO-ORGANISERS: RSE, CNR, UoY

LANGUAGE: Italian

CONCEPT

The MARINEWIND workshop focused on the latest advances on FOWTs in Italy in connection with the Horizon Europe project MARINEWIND, funded by the European Commission. More specifically, the event, hosted by the Port Authority of Bari, took place in the city of Bari in the Puglia Region, because of its proximity to the only Offshore Wind Plant in Italy, which is, nevertheless, fixed rather than floating. Therefore, Puglia Region has been chosen as case study for the workshop.

Besides the involvement of APRE as the Coordinator of the MARINEWIND project, the Italian event has been supported by the contribution of prominent Italian research centres, such as CNR and RSE (MARINEWIND partners), and of MARINEWIND Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Paola Zerilli of UoY, who are currently involved in innovative technology projects for the energy transition.

The workshop aimed at making a relevant impact on policy, financial and economic frameworks, via exchange of knowledge and an increase in citizen engagement (via a bottom-up approach), in order to overcome the current barriers to social acceptance of FOWTs, mainly due to concerns for the environmental consequences of such technologies. Therefore, the event fostered the active engagement of the stakeholders, via co-creation activities directly connected to the MARINEWIND Italian labs. Furthermore, the event presented advances in FOWT as natural and progressive insertions into the social and environmental fabric in order to promote a sustainable blue economy in Europe.

OBJECTIVES

Inspired by the specific objectives of the MARINEWIND project:

- Increasing awareness on FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and

decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.

- Encouraging social acceptance by directly involving local communities and local fishermen and by addressing any environmental issues.
- Facilitating communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and indirectly involved in Italian MARINEWIND Lab.

TARGET AUDIENCE

Following the Quintuple Helix approach, the event targeted representatives of public authorities, civil society, green innovators, academia and industry directly involved in the Italian Lab. For each specific category, the involved actors were:

- **Industry:** FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, tech/project developers, trade associations (fisheries and tourism).
- **Academia:** Scientific & Research Community.
- **Public authorities:** at European (EC, European associations, e.g., ICLEI, ERRIN), national (Ministries for Energy, for Industry and Environment) and local level (Regional authorities), maritime transport authorities, policymakers.
- **Civil society:** NGOs, civil society organisations, and citizens.
- **Green innovation:** SMEs, public/private financial investors, insurers, ecologists, environmental organisations, and natural parks.

Additionally, through dissemination activities and synergies, the event targeted actors and beneficiaries of other EU and UK funded projects and initiatives.

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: 33 participants

Figure 1 - Participants overview

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

2.1 CONTRIBUTIONS BY THE PUGLIA REGION ON THE TOPIC OF OFFSHORE WIND POWER

MARINEWIND Italian Lab, composed by APRE, RSE and CNR, with support provided by the Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Paola Zerilli of UoY, decided to organise their 1st co-creation workshop in Bari, in the Puglia Region, due to the proximity to the only Offshore Wind Plant present in Italy up to date: this plant, which is a fixed one (rather than floating), is currently in the final construction phase (by Renexia), off the port of the city of Taranto.

For this reason, considering the interest of the Puglia Region for the future development of Floating Offshore Wind Farms, it has been decided to start the workshop with a series of interventions, inputs, contributions and ideas from the authorities of the Region, in order to shed light on the enabling conditions and on the barriers to the advancement of FOWTs in the case study.

The host of the event, the **Port Authority of Bari**, in the person of its president Dr. Ugo Patroni Griffi, exposed some of the main perceived critical issues, which should be considered with holistic perspective:

- The need for a configuration of the maritime space, confrontation with issues of international law, environmental issues, (the question of the non-decisive approach on the decarbonisation of wind power, but instead a great environmental and landscape impact due to the visibility of the generators and impact on the maritime resource).
- The question of the impact on the marine resource is debated because the generators create a shaded area that repopulates the biodiversity of the sea for the benefit of fishing (aquaculture), but the problem is that the marine areas after the construction of the wind farm can no longer be exploited for fishing.
- Another point of discussion is the economic impact of the supply chain: will the plants only be installed or also produced in Italy? What role will the Puglia Region and the local economy play in the energy supply chain? Would it be possible to include parks in port energy communities?
- Then, what benefits could wind farms bring to the port system? If they will only serve to transmit energy to the grid, there won't be any, and indeed: if the park is forbidden to navigation, it will make the ports impenetrable. There is a lack of studies on accessibility to ports in this eventuality, and a forecast scenario for the next decades, both in terms of growth and impact on the port system and of environmental impact: in order not to compromise the port system, a rational planning of Offshore Wind Farms is necessary.
- The Port Authority of Bari proposes to the MARINEWIND project to organise a meeting with the presidents of the ports, to integrate the vision of the managers of the infrastructures which would be conditioned by the wind farms.

After the Port Authority, the **Department of Economic Development of the Puglia Region** participated in the workshop through its **Management of the Energy Service and Alternative and Renewable Sources**, which dedicated a speech to **the integration of offshore planning with compensation measures for maximising local repercussions**. The intervention mainly addressed the following points:

- The European (EEC Directive no. 2001/77) and national political guidelines for Italy (Legislative Decree no. 387 of 29 December 2003) already recognised plants for the production of energy from Renewable Sources of fundamental importance, declaring them

public works utility, indifferent and urgent.

- The topic of compensation measures is part of the concept of public utility. In 2005, the Italian Constitutional Court extended the compensations also to RES plants, while the Marzano law in fact only concerned fossil plants: the impact and high concentration imply the extension to RES plants as well. Furthermore, the Court emphasizes that the benefits must not be only economic.
- The first **Regional Energy Plan (PEAR) of Puglia** dates back to 2007, with a 10-year horizon, with a significant wind production figure of 8,000 GWh (4-5 GW), and a low target of 200 MW for photovoltaics. The limit of the first PEAR was to consider fossil fuels still necessary and therefore growing, going from 31,000 GWh at the time to 60,000 GWh of gas-fired thermoelectric power. Photovoltaics did much better and fossil fuels fell, refuting 2007 predictions.
- To date, the role of the State is more incisive on energy issues, also thanks to the RED II directive, albeit with the slowness of the implementing decrees: attempts are made to replace the Regions but then implementation is slow.
- 13.4 GW of power in the worst-case scenario will be the "burden sharing" for Puglia in the decade 2020-2030, a very demanding effort that encourages "gigantism" (large plants), also looking at offshore. 51.8 GW are the requests for onshore RES, 31.53 GW of power for offshore.
- Proposers are not subject to prerequisites on who can propose projects, unlike other European countries.
- The main steps expected by offshore operators in Italy are: **1)** the identification of suitable areas; **2)** the approval of the implementing decrees; **3)** the publication of the RES 2 decree; **4)** the creation of the supply chain.
- The PEAR update takes into account the hydrogen strategy, the **fight against energy poverty**, the **Renewable Energy Communities** and the **balancing of the vision between the different land and sea uses** to be considered. Puglia also grants compensation to be paid by proposers of plants, including fossil ones.
- The Puglia Region wants to replicate the energy islands model and combine the experience of energy districts in operation in Puglia with the local thermal district.
- **Possible compensations in terms of energy** presented: **1)** Production and supply of electricity for the territory; **2)** Support for the creation of local Renewable Energy Communities and sharing of plant resources by the owners of utility scale plants; **3)** Co-financing of energy income measurement (LR 42/2019); **4)** Efficiency improvement of public assets and creation of smart grids.
- The **possible ways out in terms of landscape conflict**: **1)** Compensations for obtaining landscape permits; **2)** Consider and accept the concept of **Energy Landscape**, that is to say a new meaning of man-made landscape in which the forms integrate rather than avoid each other (such as wind turbines not visible from the coast and panoramic viewpoints); **3)** Figure out the "landscape conflict", that is, of perception and interpretation of the forms of the territory and their transformations (O'Neill, Walsh, 2000; Davodeau, 2008 in Ferrario, 2018). A continuous and mutual balancing between principles and fundamental rights is required, without claims of absoluteness for any of them (sentence n. 8167/2022 of the Italian Council

of State).

The **Department of Environmental Protection of the Puglia Region** addressed the following points, concerning the **framework for MSP (Maritime Spatial Planning) for the area:**

- For the purposes of implementing directive 2014/89/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 which establishes a framework for maritime spatial planning and the implementation decree of 17 October 2016, n. 201, the maritime space of national relevance was divided into three maritime areas: **Adriatic, Central Ionian-Mediterranean, Western Mediterranean.**
- For each of these areas, the drafting of a management plan is envisaged which concerns all the waters and/or seabed beyond the coastline over which Italy has jurisdiction, with the exception of areas with "urban and rural planning governed by current provisions of law"; each maritime area subject to planning has been divided into sub-areas.
- Maritime Spatial Management Plans are integrated, inter-sectoral plans, capable of coordinating the various policies, superordinated with respect to other planning instruments, the contents of which are binding for public administrations.
- The criteria and elements considered for the definition of the sub-areas, through their optimal combination and expert judgement, were the following: national and international legal and administrative limits; morphological and oceanographic characteristics.
- **The Maritime Spatial Plans for Italy must yet be approved, therefore for now in the country there is no actual planning tool.** Within the environmental impact procedure, the evaluator assesses the consistency of the proposal also with what is already known about the MSP drafts.
- The **drafting of the Management Plans** provides that for each sub-area the following are defined: **1)** the specific medium-long term vision resulting from the analysis of the existing situation, current trends and expected and/or future developments; **2)** the specific planning objectives which represent the local declination of the strategic objectives at an international, European and national level and take into account both environmental, landscape and cultural heritage aspects, and socio-economic aspects linked to the needs of the various sectors; **3)** the planning units (PU) or areas to which specific uses are assigned, with the aim of regulating and directing their functioning and evolution, and for which measures, recommendations and guidelines are subsequently defined for carrying out the activity.
- In addition to contributing to providing useful data for the initial analysis and the expected trends and for the evaluation of the conflicts and synergies between the uses of the sea, each Region should propose the specific vision and objectives for the sub-area(s) to which it belongs as well as a zoning into planning units for the same sub-area.
- The Puglia Region, acting appropriately through the levers of sustainable development and adopting an integrated and ecosystemic approach, intends to: **1)** promote the development and harmonious, equitable and sustainable use of the sea and its resources by ensuring the management and maintenance of the ecosystem in a healthy, productive and resilient condition so that it can be a source of well-being and can provide the community with the necessary goods and services considering the cumulative impacts of the different maritime

sectors, enhancing the positive synergies between the uses of the sea and minimizing, where possible by resolving, the conflicts between the uses of the sea in favour of the more sustainable uses for the marine ecosystem; **2)** contribute to and develop a planning and management of marine and maritime activities integrated and coordinated with those on land, ensuring ecological continuity and compatibility of uses between land and sea and preserving the landscape value of coastal territories, solving or minimising the critical issues generated by land-sea interactions and enhancing their synergies; **3)** promote the protection, rational use and biological rebalancing of aquatic ecosystems, fish fauna and flora, socio-economic development and the modernisation of fishing and aquaculture; **4)** contribute to the development of supply chain infrastructure, including producer markets, wholesale fish markets, ports and landing points; **5)** implement a strategy aimed at creating a sustainable, integrated development system based on local resources, aimed at enhancing and networking the productive potential of the fisheries and aquaculture sectors, through support for innovation, the involvement of world of research and the activation of intersectoral economic levers; **6)** enhance the strategic role it plays within the Mediterranean by virtue of its geographical location by enhancing cross-border and international cooperation activities; **7)** bring the Blue Economy to the centre of development and innovation policies by adopting new strategic levers both in traditional sectors such as fishing which is subjected to a constant contraction of local fish resources and in which innovation is necessary in terms of economic and environmental sustainability and in expanding sectors such as the blue bioeconomy where research, development and experimentation are an essential competitive factor.

- The **specific objectives** are set out for each of the following sectors: **1)** Ecosystems and biodiversity; **2)** Landscape and cultural heritage and identity; **3)** Safety and legality at sea and in ports; **4)** Sustainable tourism; **5)** Development of sustainable fisheries and aquaculture; **6)** Integrated management of coastal zones and coast defence; **7)** Maritime transport and port facilities; **8)** Power; **9)** Military uses.
- Concerning the **situation of Offshore Wind Farms in Europe**, it has been pointed out that, moving further offshore enables larger sea areas with more stable wind conditions, reduces impact on other economic activities and minimises potential visual impact on the coastline. But transmission costs are higher, and construction and operation are both more expensive.
- Both German and Belgian transmission system operators (TSO) find clustering wind farms into a single offshore substation the most efficient way to bring electricity to shore.
- In **Italy**, analysing the geographical distribution of connection requests from offshore wind farms, it can be seen that these are mainly concentrated in the regions of the South and the Islands, i.e., in areas with a high availability of primary energy resources.
- Concerning the **criticalities of MSP in the Puglia Region and concessions for Offshore Wind Farms** in the area, the issue mainly regards areas with significant landscape value that could be endangered, but it must be pointed out that the unsuitable areas are not areas where there is a ban, but areas where the probability of a refusal is high.
- As comparison with the rest of EU, **France**, while approaching Maritime Spatial Planning, has selected Atlantic areas, whereas the area facing the Mediterranean has been left free from wind power. The plans for the maritime areas of all European countries can be found on the

EC websites, also to compare the approaches.

- Another problem in Italy is represented by the fact that many historic environmental associations have taken strong positions in favour of renewables, often to the detriment of landscape protection.
- In Puglia, potential for offshore installation resides in the area off the coast of the gulf of the Otranto channel, then an area off the Gargano promontory: both are **delicate in terms of landscape integrity protection**.
- The **benefits of the offshore wind farms** that the MARINEWIND project presents, such as the improvement of air quality, **must be measurable** (with the vocabulary of the Community Directive), and the positive impacts located geographically.

2.2 OVERVIEW OF REQUESTS FOR OFFSHORE WIND FARMS IN PUGLIA REGION

MARINEWIND project partner RSE – Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (Energy System Research) has presented the audience an overview of the current situation for Puglia Region regarding the quantity and characteristics of the pending request for Offshore Wind Farms. The following elements emerged from the presentation:

- In Italy, there are currently 67 applications for authorizations for offshore wind farms (of which 14 in Puglia, which boasts the highest number after Sardinia and Sicily), with a number of wind turbines equal to 3,412 (920 only in Puglia) and a power of 50.3 GW (13.7 for Puglia).
- In general, it should be noted that some projects insist on the same area, and, in some areas, there is a high density of projects. Furthermore, the only projects with fixed technology are those in Emilia Romagna. For two projects, it is interesting to point out that the plant is located off the coast of a region but the connection to the grid takes place in another region.
- The type of turbine most taken into consideration for the drafting of the projects is the 15 MW Vestas V236, of which a prototype has been installed in Denmark. It is a 15 MW horizontal axis turbine with three blades, with a rotor diameter of 236 m and a hub height of at least 150 m.
- Focusing on **Puglia Region**, and in particular in the area off the **Gargano**, in the provinces of Foggia and Barletta-Andria-Trani, 6 offshore wind farm projects were presented. All projects are located beyond the 12 nautical mile line which delimits territorial waters. Furthermore, 5 projects insist on areas with depths between 60 m and 200 m, while 1 project occupies areas with very variable depths. The projects seem partly overlapping.
- Remaining in Puglia, with the focus on the area off **Brindisi**, 3 offshore wind farm projects were presented: 1 project is located beyond the 12 nautical mile line which delimits the territorial waters, 2 projects are located within the territorial waters and are partly overlapping. The 3 projects are located in the bathymetric range between 60 m and 200 m of depth.
- For the part of Puglia facing the **Ionian Sea**, off the coast of the provinces of **Lecce and Taranto**, 5 offshore wind farm projects were presented: 2 projects are located within the 12 nautical mile line which delimits the territorial waters and are included in areas with bathymetry between 60 m and 500 m. Instead, the remaining 3 projects, overlapping each other, are located beyond the 12 nautical mile line which delimits the territorial waters, in

areas with depths between 500 m and 1,000 m.

3 ROUNDTABLES TOPICS OVERVIEW

The roundtable discussion naturally began with questions and issues from the participants to the speakers. The main points of debate, from which both critical issues emerged (which were discussed during the session) and real barriers (with which the project will have to deal with in its future activities and in the subsequent workshops, looking for possible solutions), but also incentives and enabling factors, were the following:

- The Maritime Directorate, as the first administration that receives the concession application and carries out the evaluation, has encountered various management problems: a single authorisation is envisaged, but before it can become a fluid system there is a need for sharing and in-depth analysis, feasibility studies and so on to establish whether it could be useful or not.
- The problem of the visibility of the plants (that causes damage to the landscape) cannot be resolved by not implementing FOWTs in the territory: it is necessary to assess the visibility issue, it is not right to limit areas such as, for example, high ground that is not accessible to all, not commonly usable.
- Regarding the maritime area planning, the technical participants believe that affecting the landscape is not a real problem, since in Italy projects for Wind Farms never contemplate areas with a distance from the coast shorter than 35 km.
- Technical participants explained that Italian maritime space cannot be planned properly, as it happens for mainland instead. In other European countries (such as France), planning took place after geotechnical analysis of the seabed; in Italy we proceed by hypothesis without actual studies.
- Only 18% of Italian seabed spaces has been codified and studied in terms of the feasibility. However, these studies are carried out by private entities, while public authorities should take responsibility for them, and carry on more geophysical and geotechnical assessments. On the contrary, the public authority representatives believe that this kind of studies should remain a responsibility for privates (e.g., engineering companies, technical developers and suppliers) that will gain profit from the construction of wind farms. The technical participants insisted on the fact that private studies can be publicly useful, for example for universities but also for ports (e.g., to define maritime routes).
- Furthermore, wind farms are expensive, and private entities often abandon the hypothesis of the seabed because of how problematic it is in Italy (e.g., for earthquakes, unlike the situation in Northern countries, which is more homogeneous). Therefore, from their side there is a greater thrust for FOWTs.
- In terms of costs, planning all the maritime space would cost 1 billion euros.
- The issue of economic compensation for the population most affected by the construction of wind farms has emerged. In some states, Denmark in the lead, but also in Scotland, the economic participation of local populations up to a rate of 20% of the investment is envisaged by law. In Italy, big investors are the only ones involved, not allowing small investments. We need to look at models of co-responsibility, so the population also shares

the benefits. Soon, when the costs of these new technologies are lower, then solutions like royalties will be more feasible.

- Other forms of participations by the people have been experimented in other EU countries, for example crowdfunding.
- An issue to be considered, though, is that not all the territories in Europe have the same economic background: Puglia Region situation is quite different from Denmark one, for example.
- According to some participants, it would be a social compensation more than a mere economic one: to that, the Region replies that in general economic/social compensation could be attempted if the Municipalities were ready to use that money to improve efficiency, to date the population does not see anything in terms of benefits, for example with a reduction in bills, and therefore civil society is less inclined to accept the critical issues of wind power. The regional law, for example, is open in this sense, even though Italian Constitutional Court blocked the hypothesis of strictly economic compensations.
- Unlike Italy, other European states have municipalities that are directly managers and owners of the stretch of network.
- Port Authority and Coast Guard expressed the problem of disputes that slow down the authorization processes.
- The Italian State up to date has planned only 0.9 GW, but the request is much higher, and for that there is no proper codification.
- The lack of tenders to assign the maritime areas for Wind Farms should be reported to the European Commission as an issue to be solved. For the moment, there is an unregulated race to apply for concession. A possible solution is to identify tenders to assign maritime areas, with established criteria.
- The necessity to rethink spaces and infrastructures has emerged, and in addition to make preventive investments (e.g., make ports equipped for plants).
- Technical audience explained that, to date, in Italy there is no port that is taking concrete measures to face the fact that, to achieve the 2030 objectives, we would need to build 6,000 turbines a year. The only ports equipped now are in Northern Europe, and other countries (e.g., France) are taking adapting measures. This means that in the future, if we do not equip ourselves, too, these countries will be the main suppliers of energy, to our detriment.
- Lack of regulation for operators create the problematic impact on environment, economy, landscape and so on, because it is cumulative and erratic, otherwise the technical participants do not believe Wind Farms to be harmful per se.
- The issue of limitation of other uses of the sea, such as sport fishing, has been debated, since technical participants reported that, for example, other European countries are trying to implement a proper coexistence between other uses of the sea and Offshore. This is another issue to be regulated, after having verified the possibility of navigating in safety, but, in any case, the distances between the generators are always high.
- An important benefit to be considered is the fact that there will be a commitment to make wind farms protected areas of aquaculture, therefore, in the neighbouring areas there will be more abundance of fish. Ban will stay only, for example, for trawling, but otherwise offshore will impact positively the environment, the species will reproduce creating more population

to fish.

- Therefore, another enabling factor is the fact that the maritime space given in concession for wind farm can also be used for other types of renewable energy, such as floating solar energy, increasing the energy density while occupying the same area (for example, today the Adriatic is penalized in terms of windiness, so if installing photovoltaic panels would be an advantage).
- An enabling factor would be to allow the local enterprises organisation to conduct a proper screen of local enterprises to understand which ones could be involved in the process of FOWTs implementation, rooting the Wind Farms inside the socioeconomic fabric of the most affected municipalities (connected to the idea of energy communities and shared management of the resources). The aim could be reaching a form of autarky in these areas.

4 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

A survey on the MENTIMETER tool was prepared by APRE, RSE, CNR and UoY and submitted to the participants in the final part of the workshop, in order to collect useful data.

Figure 2 - MENTIMETER Tool Question 1

The question regarding the category to which the participants belonged highlighted an overall balance in the participation between institutions, universities & research centres and industry players, while the participating associations were fewer (although representatives of civil society also classified themselves as "other").

Quali sono i fattori abilitanti più importanti per poter investire in FOWT?

Figure 3 - MENTIMETER Tool Question 2

According to the participants, the most important enabling factors for investing in FOWTs are, in order: a clear regulatory framework (which quadrupled the other responses), the development potential of the supply chain at the local level on par with the technological maturity, and, finally, the presence of incentives. No participant opted for the answers "national transmission grid stability" and "large market share and demand".

Dove è il rischio più importante nella supply chain secondo voi?

Figure 4 - MENTIMETER Tool Question 3

Regarding the risks for the supply chain, the most significant were found out to be: the development of adequate infrastructure (with 14 responses out of 19) and the capacity of the supply chain at the local level (with 5 responses). No participant opted for the answer "availability of ad hoc vessels for the installation of the turbines".

Figure 5 - MENTIMETER Tool Question 4

To the open question "What aspects do you think are relevant, in Italy, to encourage the diffusion of FOWTs in a sustainable way and in respect of the other uses of the sea?", the most interesting answers were: the preparation of a long-term planning, the improvement of the regulatory framework, a rethinking of the incentive policies for local communities and the entire distribution network, the consideration for the compatibility with the tourist vocation of many maritime areas, the development of technologies that both limit the impact on the marine environment and bring positive effects on the entire Italian production system.

Figure 6 - MENTIMETER Tool Question 5

Instead, speaking of the critical aspects, the participants answered, among other things: the failure to identify areas specifically suited to the location on the basis of energy needs and grant them through tender, the disinformation made by some environmental associations, as well as the failure to disseminate knowledge relating to offshore wind plants and farm, and the benefits of procurement compared to other sources.

Quali altri usi del mare vanno presi in considerazione nel pianificare la diffusione dell'eolico offshore per uno sviluppo consapevole e condiviso? 14 Risposte

Figure 7 - MENTIMETER Tool Question 6

According to almost all of the participants, the other uses of the sea that absolutely must be taken into consideration were the following: navigation, fishing, tourism, other multipurpose platforms (photovoltaic, H2), aquaculture and the development of new biodiversity.

Come coinvolgere attivamente la società civile

Figure 8 - MENTIMETER Tool Question 7

There have been various ways of actively and effectively involving civil society in the debate and planning of the next scenarios for FOWTs in Italy, including: encouraging local energy autonomy (with the participation of the municipalities concerned), proposing estimates of new jobs work that would be created and on savings in bills for citizens, but above all to inform about benefits for health, for the environment and about compensations, economic incentives and productivity,

Figure 9 - MENTIMETER Tool Question 8

The sector that most conflicted with the offshore wind sector was shipping, closely followed by environmental conservation, then fishing and tourism.

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The 1st of the three co-creation workshops for T1.3 with regards to the Italian Lab has been mainly dedicated to barriers perceived by the stakeholders for the investment on FOWTs, and to potential enablers. Thanks to the data collected, the next two workshops will then focus on solutions and policies to ease the installation of Offshore Wind Plants. The table below summarises the main barriers, criticalities and bottlenecks identified during the workshop on one side, and the most significant enablers and incentives on the other.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
Unclear regulatory framework for the concession of maritime spaces.	Wind farms would become protected areas, encouraging aquaculture and increasing biodiversity.
Lack of proper Maritime Spatial Planning (still in draft).	Aquaculture would bring benefits to fishing, increasing the fish population and therefore the levels of catch in the neighbouring areas.
Blocking access to ports, and in general impairment of the functioning of the port system.	Economic advantages for local enterprises of any direct participation in the supply chain.
Problem in the division of responsibilities between public and private entities regarding feasibility studies and preliminary analyses (for example, of the seabed).	Detailed information and advertising of health benefits (e.g., through quantitative measurements of improvement of air quality) and new job positions. In general, on the long-term economic effects, for example the non-exclusion of Italy as an energy provider after 2030.

Obstacle to the use of other uses of the sea and related sectors involved (first navigation, then landscape integrity and environmental protection, fishing both as a commercial and recreational and sporting activity, tourism).	Integration of wind farms into the socio-economic fabric of the territories concerned, for example through the establishment of energy communities in ports.
Confusion in the allocation of tasks between state and regional bodies.	Investments involving the population (for example crowdfunding) on the model of Denmark. Therefore, legislative regulation of the participation of small investors, bringing as consequence shared responsibility and economic and social benefits, that will help overcoming prejudices and concerns by the civil society.
Lack of tenders (with established criteria) to assign the maritime areas for Wind Farms, and consequent unregulated race to apply for concession.	Use the maritime zones granted for wind farms also for the implementation of other forms of renewable energy (for example, offshore floating photovoltaics).
Lack of regulation for private operators in the field, for now erratic, thus creating problematic and cumulative impacts on environment, economy, landscape, fruition of the sea and tourism.	Economic incentives for implementation.
Lack of a smooth single authorisation procedure and of interventions to streamline the resolution of disputes and disputes that block the approval of projects for years.	National planning on the long term.
Lack of geotechnical and geophysical assessments for Italian seabed.	Implementation of coexistence measures between wind farms and other uses of the sea (e.g., not blocking the area to navigation, also reassuring on the safety conditions).
	Adaptation of existing infrastructure (e.g., ports), and preventive investment in new infrastructure.